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Awareness And Prevention Practices Of Hepatitis B Infection Among Women Attending Antenatal Clinics In Primary Health Care Facilities In Osogbo, Osun State

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ABSTRACT

Despite the increasing implementation of vaccines and passive immunization, management of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection remains a persistent challenge in many areas globally. There is a gap in knowledge on awareness of HBV infection, transmission route of HBV, prevention measures, and compliance to prevention measures of HBV among pregnant women. This study focused on assessing the level of hepatitis B virus infection awareness and prevention among pregnant women attending antenatal care in selected primary health care facilities in Oshogbo, Osun state.

This was a cross-sectional study among women attending antenatal care services in selected health care facilities in Osogbo. A stratified random sampling method was employed in this study. A questionnaire containing four sections was designed as instrument for data collection. A total of three hundred questionnaire was retrieved from three hundred and sixteen. The outcome variable for this study was awareness of HBV infection and compliance with preventive measures. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Frequency and percentage distributions, mean and standard deviations, chi-square test of association, and binary logistic regression were used in the analysis. The chi-square test was used to explore factors associated with awareness of HBV infection as well as compliance with preventive measures and binary logistic regression was used to examine the factors influencing awareness of HBV infection as well as compliance with preventive measures. Variables were considered statistically significant at a P value <0.05. A lot 115 (38.3%) of the respondents had a poor level of awareness of HBV infection. 61.7% of the sample size had a poor level of awareness about HBV prevention measures. A lot 202 (67.3%) of the participants had poor compliance with HBV prevention measures. These findings revealed a poor level of awareness about HBV infection, HBV transmission routes, and HBV prevention measures as well as compliance with HBV preventive measures. Also, the study identified that self-employed women and those who were into business were less likely to have a good level of awareness and civil servants were more likely to comply with HBV preventive measures. Strategies targeted towards improving knowledge and awareness about HBV infection as well as its practice of preventive measures are needed among women attending antenatal care services.

Keywords: Hepatitis B virus, vaccine, Awareness, Transmission, prevention, antenatal

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) remains a major global health challenge, causing both acute and chronic liver disease, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) (Albashir et al., 2024; Bhattacharya et al., 2025; Yao-Chun Hsu & Mindie H. Nguyen, 2024). HBV is a small, partially double-stranded DNA

virus of the Hepadnaviridae family, with a genome of about 3.2 kb and four overlapping genes (S, C, P, X) (Chunzheng Li et al., 2024). The virus is transmitted through perinatal (mother-to-child), sexual, and parenteral routes, including exposure to infected blood or body fluids, unsafe injections, and tattooing (Albashir et al., 2024; Bhattacharya et al., 2025; Li et al., 2024).

Globally, an estimated 254–296 million people are living with chronic HBV infection as of 2024, with the highest burdens in the Western Pacific and African regions (Albashir et al., 2024; Dagnaw et al., 2025; Bhattacharya et al., 2025). HBV is 50–100 times more infectious than HIV, and the risk of chronic infection is highest when transmission occurs perinatally or in early childhood (Hobart et al., 2024; Tohme et al., 2024). In high-prevalence regions such as sub-Saharan Africa and parts of Asia, perinatal and early childhood transmission predominate, while in low-prevalence areas, sexual and parenteral exposures are more common (Hobart et al., 2024; Kaewdech et al., 2024).

Chronic HBV infection can be asymptomatic or lead to chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, and HCC. In 2022, HBV was responsible for over 820,000 deaths globally, mainly due to cirrhosis and liver cancer (Albashir et al., 2024; Dagnaw et al., 2025). In Africa, HBV accounts for approximately half of all HCC cases (Albashir et al., 2024). Risk factors for infection include transfusion of unscreened blood, unsafe injections, sexual contact, tattooing, healthcare work, and close contact with infected individuals (Bhattacharya et al., 2025; Chunzheng et al., 2024).

Universal HBV vaccination is the most effective strategy for prevention, with the World Health Organization (WHO) targeting 90% coverage by 2030 (Al-Busafi & Ahmed, 2024; Apichat et al., 2024). However, global birth dose coverage remains suboptimal, especially in low-resource settings (Tohme et al., 2024; Gong et al., 2024; Van de Ven and Johnson, 2006). In some high-risk groups, such as healthcare workers, vaccination rates are still insufficient (Orotta et al., 2025; Berhanu et al., 2025).

Despite advances in vaccination and antiviral therapy, HBV remains underdiagnosed and undertreated, with only a small fraction of eligible patients receiving care (Yao-Chun & Mindie Nguyen, 2024; Al-Busafi & Ahmed, 2024). Social stigma, limited healthcare access, and gaps in prevention and treatment programs continue to hinder elimination efforts (Yao-Chun & Mindie Nguyen, 2024; Tassew et al., 2024).

General Objective

The study aims to assess the level of hepatitis B virus infection awareness and prevention among pregnant women attending antenatal care in selected primary health facilities in Osogbo.

Specific Objectives

1. To assess the level of awareness of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women attending selected health facilities in Osogbo.
2. To determine the level of compliance with preventive measures against hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women in the selected primary health facilities in Osogbo Osun State.
3. To assess the factors influencing awareness of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women in the selected primary health facilities in Osogbo, Osun State.
4. To assess the factors influencing prevention of hepatitis B virus infection among pregnant women in selected primary health facilities in Osogbo, Osun State

Research Questions

1. Do women in selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo, Osun State know about hepatitis B virus infection?
2. Do women in selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo, Osun State know about the prevention of hepatitis B virus infection?
3. What are the factors influencing awareness of the hepatitis B virus among women attending the selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo, Osun State?
4. What are the factors influencing the prevention of the Hepatitis B virus among women attending the selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo, Osun State?

Research Hypothesis

1. Women attending the selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo have no significant knowledge of hepatitis B virus infection.

2. Women attending the selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo do not significantly practice preventive measures against hepatitis B virus infection.
3. Women attending the selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo have a significantly low level of awareness.
4. There are no significant association among factors influencing the practice of hepatitis B virus infection preventing strategies among women attending primary health care facilities in Osogbo.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Setting

The study was carried out in Oshogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. Osogbo is the capital city of Osun State which was established in 1991. Osogbo shares boundaries with Ikirun, Ilesa, Ede, Egbedore, and Iragbiji. Osogbo has a population of 750,000 according to 2022. Population and Housing Commission Census and it is mostly dominated by the Yoruba. Osogbo sometimes called Ile Aro is a major dyeing center and one of the industries in Osogbo. Osogbo is also the venue of the annual Osun-Osogbo festival along the River Osun. There are two major local governments in Osogbo namely, Osogbo local government, and Olorunda local government.

3.2 Research Design

This is a descriptive design of the cross-sectional survey type carried out among pregnant women attending antenatal services in the selected primary health care facilities in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. To achieve the objectives of this study and be able to present the patterns of the variables of interest, a cross-sectional study design, which is majorly used to assess the prevalence of the population was used in this study.

3.3 Target Population Of Study

The population for this study included women attending antenatal clinics in the selected primary health facilities in Osogbo local government and Olorunda local government.

3.3.1 Inclusion Criteria

Pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in the selected primary health facilities in Osogbo township, Osun State, Nigeria with adequate physical, mental, and cognitive capacity were willing to participate in the survey.

3.3.2 Exclusion Criteria

Pregnant women who were not physically and health wisely fit to participate were excluded from this study.

3.4 Research Sampling Methods

A three-stage multistage sampling technique was used in this study. The first stage was the selection of the two Local Government Areas (LGA) in Osogbo. The second stage was the random selection of six health facilities (three from Olorunda LGA and three from Osogbo LGA) in Osogbo, Osun state. This resulted in 6 PHC facilities namely: Isale-Agbara PHC, Oke-Baale PHC, Odi-Olowo PHC, Sabo PHC, Oluode PHC, and Ota-Efun PHC. The second stage was achieved by balloting to avoid bias in the selection of primary health facilities. The names of each primary health facility were written on pieces of paper and were wrapped. After which it was mixed and a random selection of three primary health facilities was done from each local government area. The three randomly selected primary health facilities under Osogbo LGA included Isale-Agbara PHC, Oke-Baale PHC, and Odi-Olowo PHC. Health facilities selected in Olorunda LGA included Sabo PHC, Oluode PHC, and Ota-Efun PHC.

The third stage was a simple random selection of pregnant women coming for antenatal care services in the selected hospitals. All eligible patients that visited the study facilities were approached, and the study was explained to them, and those who gave consent were enrolled in this study.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

Using the Leslie- Kish formulae.

$$n = \frac{Z_a^2 pq}{d^2} \text{ (Leslie-Kish formula)}$$

Where,

n = minimum sample size

Z = Standard deviate at 95% confidence interval = 1.96

p = Prevalence (Hang Pham *et al.*, 2019).

q = Complimentary Probability to P

d = Error Margin = 5% = 0.05

(Where; $z^2 = 1.96^2$, $p = 0.75$, $q = 1-p = 0.25$, $d^2 = 0.05^2$)

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.75 \times 0.25}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.75 \times 0.25}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 288$$

A 10% non-response rate was adjusted for, this led to a total sample size of 316 calculated for this study.

3.6 Research Instrument For Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire contained demographic questions, which elicited basic information from the respondents, such as their ages, sex, and other details. The questionnaire was set up in an electronic data collection tool Kobo toolbox and data were captured on the android application. Each participant that gave consent was interviewed by myself and a research assistant using the questions from the app and responses were entered on the app and submitted to the Kobo humanitarian server from which data were exported into data analysis software SPSS 25.

3.7 Method Of Data Analysis

Analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Frequency and percentage tables, charts, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize the data as appropriate. Also, the Chi-square test of association was used to assess factors associated with awareness of HBV infections and compliance with HBV prevention measures. Binary logistic regression was used to examine the factors influencing awareness of HBV infections, and compliance with HBV prevention measures. Variables were considered statistically significant at P-value < 5%.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration was sought and obtained from Adeleke University Ethics Review Committee before going to the field for data collection. Written informed consent was made available in the questionnaire. The confidentiality of all respondents was ensured by excluding the use of identifiers such as names, addresses, and other information that can reveal the identity of research participants. This research did pose any harm to the participants. The participants were addressed and ensured of their confidentiality.

3.9.1 Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained from participants involved in the study after explaining the purpose of the study to them.

3.9.2 Confidentiality Of Data

To ensure confidentiality, no names were recorded on the study instruments. Code numbers were assigned to questionnaires for easy tracking. Study instruments were kept in a safe place and were only accessible to members of the research.

3.10 Validity/ Reliability Of Research Instrument

Validity of the research instruments (the questionnaire) was carried out. It was corrected by the supervisor to assess it and determine the appropriateness and relevance of the questions in the instruments before proceeding to the field for actual study.

In testing for the reliability of the research instrument, pre-test was conducted for 10% of sample size. The obtained from the analysis was used to check for the consistency of the survey before carrying out a full field work.

RESULTS

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the study participants

The results in table 4.1 presented the demographic information of the study participants. Participants were approached and those who consented provided responses that were available to them. The question-specific non-response rate ranged from 5 (1.7%) to 23(7.7%). The mean age of the respondents was 27.7 ± 2.60 SD. Also, 23 (8.3%) of them were aged <20 years and 156 (56.3%) were aged 30 to 30 years. Majority 130 (44.1%) of the respondents were in business/ trading, 112 (38.0%) were self-employed, and 53 (18.0%) were Civil servants. Most of them 278 (92.7%) were in a union, and 22 (7.3%) were not in any union. About 265 (88.3%) were Yoruba, while the other 35(11.7%) comprised Igbos and Hausas

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the study participants

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age as at last birthday		
<20	23	8.3
20-30	156	56.3
31-40	98	35.4
Occupation		
Self-employed	112	38.0
Business/Trading	130	44.1
Civil servant	53	18.0
Marital Status		
Not in a union	22	7.3
In a union	278	92.7
Ethnicity		
Yoruba	265	88.3
Others (Igbo, Hausa)	35	11.7

4.2 Level and pattern of awareness of HBV infection among pregnant women in selected health facilities in Osogbo, Osun State

The results in figure 1 and table 4.2 presented the level and pattern of HBV infection awareness among the study participants respectively. Overall, 115 (38.3%) of the respondents had a poor level of awareness of HBV infection. Going by specific indicators of HBV awareness, only 138 (46.0%) have heard about HBV. About 97 (52.7%) heard from the radio, 36 (19.6%) heard from the television, and 51 (27.7%) read from the newspaper. Also, only 87 (30.0%) said HBV is a communicable infection, and 99 (35.0%) said they were aware of what chronic infection can cause

Figure 1 Level of awareness of HBV infection among pregnant women in selected health facilities in Osogbo, Osun State

Table 4.2: Pattern of awareness of HBV infection among pregnant women in selected health facilities in Osogbo, Osun State

Items	Frequency	Percent
Have you ever heard of Hepatitis B Virus?		
Yes	138	46.0
Not sure	6	2.0
Not	156	52.0
What was your source of information?		
Radio	97	52.7
Television	36	19.6
Newspaper	51	27.7
Is HBV a communicable infection?		
Yes	87	30.0
Not sure	82	28.3
No	121	41.7
Do you know what chronic HBV infection can cause?		
Yes	99	35.0
Not sure	75	26.5
No	109	38.5

4.3 Awareness of transmission routes of HBV among the participants

The results presented in table 4.3 showed participants' awareness of transmission routes of HBV. About 148 (49.3%) said HBV can be transmitted through a handshake, 52.5% said it can be transmitted through contaminated water, and 248 (84.1%) said HBV can be transmitted through unprotected sex, and 220 (77.7%) said it can be transmitted through blood transfusion. Similarly, about 149 (50.5%) said HBV can be transmitted through sneezing or coughing, 231 (81.6%) said it can be transmitted from mother to children, and 143 (51.4%) said HBV can be transmitted through eating with or sharing food/utensils

Table 4.3: Awareness of transmission routes of HBV among the participants

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Can hepatitis B be transmitted through handshake?		
Yes	148	49.3
Not sure	60	20.0
No	92	30.7
Can hepatitis B be transmitted through contaminated water?		
Yes	155	52.5
Not sure	71	24.1
No	69	23.4
Can hepatitis B be transmitted through unprotected sex?		
Yes	248	84.1
Not sure	30	10.2
No	17	5.8
Can hepatitis B be transmitted through blood transfusion?		
Yes	220	77.7
Not sure	40	14.1
No	23	8.1
Can hepatitis B be transmitted through sneezing or coughing?		
Yes	149	50.5
Not sure	89	30.2
No	57	19.3
Can hepatitis B be transmitted from mother to child?		
Yes	231	81.6
Not Sure	41	14.5
No	11	3.9
Can hepatitis B be transmitted through eating with or sharing food/utensils?		
Yes	143	51.4
Not sure	83	29.9
No	52	18.7

4.4 Level and pattern of awareness about HBV prevention measures

The results in figure 2 and table 4.4 showed the level and pattern of awareness about HBV prevention measures respectively. About 61.7% of the study population had a poor level of awareness about HBV prevention measures. The pattern of awareness about HBV prevention measures revealed that 142 (48.1%) of the participants said cleaning and cooking food thoroughly prevents HBV transmission. About 249 (84.4%) said the HBV vaccine prevents HBV transmission. Also, 225 (77.9%) said HBV transmission can be prevented by not reusing or sharing needles/syringes. Similarly, 142 (48.1%) said can HBV transmission be prevented by avoiding sharing food/utensils or eating with a person with chronic HBV. In the same vein, 237 (82.0%) said using a condom for sexual intercourse can prevent HBV transmission.

Figure 2: Level of awareness about HBV prevention measures

Table 4.4: Level and pattern of awareness about HBV prevention measures

Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
Cleaning and cooking food thoroughly prevent HBV transmission.		
Yes	142	48.1
Not sure	100	33.9
No	53	18.0
Hepatitis B vaccine prevent HBV transmission?		
Yes	249	84.4
Not sure	46	15.6
HBV transmission can be prevented by not reusing or sharing needles/syringes?		
Yes	225	77.9
Not sure	64	22.1
Can HBV transmission be prevented by avoid sharing food/utensils or eating with a person with chronic HBV?		
Yes	142	48.1
Not sure	112	38.0
No	41	13.9
Can using a condom prevent HBV transmission?		
Yes	237	82.0
Not sure	35	12.1
No	17	5.9

4.5 Awareness of mother-to-child HBV prevention

The information on awareness about mother-to-child HBV prevention was presented in table 4.5. Most 265 (93.6%) of the participants said it is needed to be tested for HBV as a pregnant women. Also, the majority 242 (83.7%) said HBV vaccination is necessary for infants. Many 184 (77.6%) of the women said the best time to provide a healthy and stable child with the first dose of HBV vaccine is “at birth”. Also, 179/191 of the women said vaccination is the measure that could protect the newborn if the pregnant woman has chronic HBV.

Table 4.5: Awareness of mother to child HBV prevention

Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
As a pregnant woman, do you need to be tested for HBV?		
Yes	265	93.6
Not sure	6	2.1
No	12	4.2
Is HBV vaccination necessary for your infant?		
Yes	242	83.7
Not sure	30	10.4
No	17	5.9
When is the best time to provide a healthy and stable child the first dose of HBV vaccine?		
At birth	184	77.6
During immunization	53	22.4
If a pregnant woman has chronic HBV, what measure could protect the newborn from becoming infected?		
Vaccination	179	93.7
Drug administration	12	6.3

4.6 Level and pattern of compliance with HBV prevention measures

The results presented in figure 3 and table 4.6 showed the level and pattern of compliance with HBV prevention measures. A lot 202 (67.3%) of the participants had poor compliance with HBV prevention measures. Also, only 26.7% (80/300) were vaccinated against HBV, and the reasons for not taking the vaccine were unawareness (39.1%) and unwillingness (60.9%). Although, majority (88.3%) of them had one sexual partner. But only 33.2% have tested for HBV and 12.4% said their partner had tested for HBV. Also, 62 (31.3%) of them said they have a body piercing/tattoo.

Table 4.6: Pattern of compliance with HBV prevention measures

Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
Are you vaccinated against HBV?		
Yes	80	26.7
No	220	73.3
If not, why?		
I have not heard about it	86	39.1
Not willing	134	60.9
How many sexual partners do you have?		
One	265	88.3
Preferred not to say	35	11.7
Have you been tested for HBV?		
Yes	98	33.2
No	197	66.8
Has your partner been tested for HBV?		
Yes	35	12.4
No	248	87.6
Do you have any body piercings or tattoos?		
Yes	62	31.3
No	136	68.7

4.7 Factors associated with awareness of HBV infection

Table 4.7 presents the results of the factors associated with awareness of HBV infection and some demographic characteristics. Good level of awareness was more common (70.4%) among women aged 31 – 40 years compared to age 20 – 30 years (56.4%) and below 20 years (47.8%), P= 0.036. Also, a good level of awareness was more pronounced (64.7%) among women who were in a union compared to those (22.7%) who were not in a union, P<0.001, In the same vein, the result showed that higher (77.4%) proportion of civil servants had a good level of awareness liken to those who were into business/trading (53.1%) and those who were self-employed (62.5%), P=0.009. More (63.4%) of Yoruba women had a good level of awareness about HBV infections compared to other ethnic groups (48.6%), P=0.090.

Table 4.7: Factors associated with awareness of HBV infection
Awareness of HBV prevention

Variables	Poor level of awareness (score below 5)	Good level of awareness (score 5 - 10)	Chi square	P value
Age as at last birthday			6.67	0.036
<20	12(52.2)	11(47.8)		
20-30	68(43.6)	88(56.4)		
31-40	29(29.6)	69(70.4)		
Marital Status			15.23	0.000
Not in a union	17(77.3)	5(22.7)		
In a union	98(35.3)	180(64.7)		
Occupation			9.49	0.009
Self-employed	42(37.5)	70(62.5)		
Business/Trading	61(46.9)	69(53.1)		
Civil servant	12(22.6)	41(77.4)		
Ethnicity			2.87	0.090
Yoruba	97(36.6)	168(63.4)		
Other (Igbo, Hausa)	18(51.4)	17(48.6)		

4.8 Factors influencing awareness of HBV infection

As presented in table 4.8, the binary logistic regression showed that self-employed women (OR=0.40, P=0.003, 95%CI: 0.22 – 0.73) and Businesswomen (OR=0.42, P=0.081, 95%CI: 0.16 – 1.11) were less likely to have a good level of awareness compared to civil servants

Table 4.8: Factors influencing awareness of HBV infection

Variables	OR	P value	95% C.I. Lower	Upper
Age as at last birthday				
<20	Ref			
20-30	0.25	0.116	0.04	1.41
31-40	0.63	0.568	0.13	3.13
Occupation				
Self-employed	0.40	0.003	0.22	0.73
Business/Trading	0.42	0.081	0.16	1.11
Civil servant	Ref			
Marital Status				
Not in a union	0.80	0.998	0.01	8.02

In a union	Ref			
Ethnicity				
Yoruba	Ref			
Other (Igbo, Hausa)	0.30	0.085	0.08	1.18

4.9 Factors associated with compliance with HBV prevention measures

The results in table 4.9 presented the factors associated with compliance with HBV prevention measures. There was a higher (77.4%) proportion of the good level of compliance among civil servants compared to self-employed (20.5%) and Businesswomen (26.2%), $P < 0.001$. Also, a good level of compliance was more pronounced among Yoruba (34.7%) women compared to other ethnic groups (17.1%), $P = 0.037$.

Table 4.9: Factors associated with compliance with HBV prevention measures

Variables	Poor level of prevention compliance (score below 3)	Good level of prevention compliance (score 3- 5)	Chi-square	P value
Age as at last birthday			0.91	0.634
<20	17(73.9)	6(26.1)		
20-30	109(69.9)	47(30.1)		
31-40	64(65.3)	34(34.7)		
Marital Status			1.77	0.184
Not in a union	12(54.5)	10(45.5)		
In a union	190(68.3)	88(31.7)		
Occupation			57.59	0.000
Self-employed	89(79.5)	23(20.5)		
Business/Trading	96(73.8)	34(26.2)		
Civil servant	12(22.6)	41(77.4)		
Ethnicity			4.34	0.037
Yoruba	173(65.3)	92(34.7)		
Other (Igbo, Hausa)	29(82.9)	6(17.1)		

4.10 Factors influencing compliance with HBV prevention measures

Table 4.10 presents the factors associated with compliance with HBV prevention measures. It was found that civil servants (OR=4.44, $P = 0.003$, 95% CI=1.64 – 12.03) were more likely to have a good level of compliance with HBV prevention measures compared to self-employed women.

Table 4.10 Factors influencing compliance with HBV prevention measures

Variables	OR	P value	95% C.I.	
			Lower	Upper
Age as at last birthday				
<20	Ref			
20-30	0.62	0.570	0.12	3.29
31-40	0.63	0.557	0.13	2.95
Occupation				
Self-employed/ students	Ref			
Business/Trading	1.20	0.585	0.62	2.34
Civil servant	4.44	0.003	1.64	12.03
Marital Status				
Not in a union	0.46	0.323	0.10	2.16
In a union	Ref			

Ethnicity

Yoruba	Ref			
Other (Igbo, Hausa)	0.48	0.314	0.12	1.98

DISCUSSION

This study was carried out among pregnant women attending antenatal care in the selected primary health facilities in Oshogbo, Osun state. The study focused on assessing the level and pattern of awareness about HBV infection, the pattern of HBV transmission route, the level, and pattern of compliance with HBV prevention guidelines, factors influencing awareness of HBV infection as well as factors influencing compliance with HBV prevention measures. Women who visited the selected P.H.C facilities were approached and those who consented to participate in this study were enrolled. The mean age of the respondents was 27.7 ±2.60 SD. The majority of the respondents were into business/ trading, some were self-employed, while others were Civil servants. Most of the women who participated in this study were in a union. Since this study was carried out in the southwest which was dominated by the Yoruba ethnic group, most of the study participants were Yorubas and other ethnic groups that participated in this study were Igbos and Hausas.

The findings of this study revealed a generally low level of awareness about Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) infection among women attending antenatal clinics in Osun State. This level of awareness was found to be lower than that reported in studies conducted among the general population in Nigeria and among specific occupational groups such as traders (Al-Busafi & Alwassief, 2024; Bhattacharya et al., 2025; Hsu & Nguyen, 2024). The variation in awareness levels may be attributed to differences in study settings and the extent of exposure to health education interventions. Hospital settings, where this study was conducted, are typically expected to promote health education and information sharing; however, the findings suggest that dissemination may not be reaching the intended audience effectively (Tohme et al., 2024; Gong et al., 2024).

Less than half of the respondents (46%) had ever heard of HBV infection, indicating significant gaps in awareness and health communication. This finding aligns with the global concern that insufficient awareness remains one of the major barriers to achieving the World Health Organization’s HBV elimination targets (Tohme et al., 2024). The observed gap between knowledge and preventive practice reinforces the assertion by Nguyen (2024) and Van de Ven and Johnson (2006) that the level of knowledge directly influences the extent of preventive practice within a population.

With respect to transmission routes, most respondents correctly identified unprotected sexual intercourse, blood transfusion, and mother-to-child transmission as possible modes of HBV infection. However, misconceptions were still prevalent, as nearly half of the respondents believed HBV could be transmitted through handshakes, sharing utensils, or consuming contaminated water. This misconception pattern mirrors the findings of previous studies in developing contexts, where limited access to accurate health education contributes to persistent misinformation (Li et al., 2024). In contrast, studies conducted in high-income countries have demonstrated higher awareness levels and fewer misconceptions, largely due to more robust public health campaigns and better access to information (Kaewdech et al., 2024).

The study also found a poor level of awareness regarding HBV prevention measures. While some respondents recognized the preventive role of vaccination, the avoidance of sharing sharp objects, and the importance of using condoms during sexual intercourse, misconceptions persisted. These findings are consistent with the observations of Tohme et al. (2024), who reported that despite global vaccination campaigns, awareness of specific preventive actions remains limited in many low- and middle-income countries. Encouragingly, about half of the respondents in this study acknowledged awareness of HBV preventive measures, reflecting ongoing efforts in health education even though the coverage remains suboptimal.

In terms of preventive behavior, two out of every three women attending antenatal clinics demonstrated poor compliance with HBV prevention practices. This aligns with the findings of Gong et al. (2024), who emphasized that limited awareness and weak behavioral change communication strategies contribute to poor adherence to preventive guidelines. The novelty of this study lies in its focus on pregnant women—a group that has received relatively little attention in previous HBV

compliance studies, which have typically concentrated on healthcare workers or the general population. Given the vulnerability of pregnant women and their infants, the low level of compliance underscores the need for intensified intervention strategies within antenatal settings.

Socio-demographic factors also played a significant role in determining awareness and compliance levels. Self-employed women and those engaged in informal business activities were found to have lower levels of HBV awareness and compliance compared to civil servants. This finding corroborates the observations of Gong et al. (2024) and Van de Ven and Johnson (2006), who noted that individuals working in structured institutional environments tend to have greater access to health information and are more likely to adopt recommended preventive behaviors. The implication is clear: public health education efforts should particularly target women in the informal sector, who may have limited exposure to organized health promotion programs.

In summary, the findings of this study highlight significant gaps in awareness and compliance with HBV prevention among antenatal women in Osun State. These results emphasize the urgent need for tailored educational interventions within healthcare facilities and community settings to enhance HBV awareness, dispel misconceptions, and improve adherence to preventive practices, especially among socioeconomically disadvantaged groups.

CONCLUSION

This finding is consistent with other findings revealing a poor level of awareness about HBV infection, HBV transmission routes and HBV prevention measures, and compliance with HBV preventive measures. This study identified that self-employed women and those who were into business were less likely to have a good level of awareness and civil servants were more likely to comply with HBV preventive measures.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Strategies such as campaigns, seminars, and training should be targeted toward the improvement of knowledge and awareness about HBV infection as well as its preventive measures among women attending antenatal care services. Also, improving the level of HBV care in routine care for pregnant women may help improve the level of prevention practice of HBV prevention measures. Timely and specific dissemination of health information will be a necessity to combat and flatten the curve of HBV infection among pregnant women and the general population

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